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Revolutionary energy storage cycle with carbon free aluminium

D2.2 Report on flexibility and compatibility with local or distributed energy production

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Foreword

REVEAL is a development project funded under the Horizon Europe funding scheme, that started in July 2022 and ends in June 2026. its principal goal is the development of a revolutionary energy storage cycle that is based on carbon free aluminium as an energy carrier, that can be used to store renewable energy also over longer time periods of months or seasons.

The **game-changing and unique solution** of the REVEAL project is using the conversion of aluminium oxide into elementary aluminium (Power-to-Al) to store renewable energy and produce a "renewable fuel" that can be **stored loss-free** for **any desired time**. In winter, when most energy is needed for space heating and electric energy prices are high, **renewable Al fuel is converted to heat and electricity** in order to cover low temperature heat and electricity demand of buildings, or to cover energy demand for processes by providing high temperature heat and hydrogen.

Thus, REVEAL will provide a backbone for heat and electricity supply of buildings in winter, in particular for climates and regions with substantial heat demand and low renewable energy potential in this season.

Two main technical developments will be taken from TRL 3 to TRL 4: First, **Power-to-Alu**: the conversion of (renewable) electricity into an Al renewable fuel with innovative inert anode technology that reduces direct CO₂-emissions of this process to zero. And second, **Alu-to-Energy**: the conversion of Al renewable fuel to useful heat and electricity for space heating and electricity supply of buildings or for process heat.

This document is a public deliverable, submitted in month 22 out of 48 project months, thus it is presenting the interim findings and expectations to energy flexibility of the main technical processes developed.

The answers that this report and deliverable shall provide turn around the question, to what extent the processes of storage charging and discharging provide flexibilities that can be used to absorb or provide electricity (and heat) on demand in a future energy system with large penetration of fluctuating renewable electricity production. The two key processes to be looked at are the charging by Power-to-Alu, i.e. inert electrode aluminium smelting, and the discharging by Alu-to-Energy, i.e. the production of heat and electricity from aluminium water reactions and fuel cells.

The presented results are to be viewed in the context of the low TRL of 3--4 of the key technologies that are analysed. This means that still much can change while developing and upscaling these technologies further, and the presented results correspond to the best knowledge and calculation that the experts can present at this stage of development.

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Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

AC	Alternating Current
Al	aluminium
CR	Cryolite ratio of the electrolyte, $CR = (KF+NaF)/AlF_3$
DC	Direct Current
HH	Hall-Hérout
KR	ratio of KF over total of KF and NaF in the electrolyte, $R=KF/(NaF+KF)$
OST	Eastern Switzerland University of Applied Sciences (Ostschweizer Fachhochschule)
PEM	Proton Exchange Membrane
PV	photovoltaic
TRL	Technology Readiness Level

1. Introduction

Use of renewable and sustainable energy sources

To achieve global climate targets, humankind will need to drastically cut emissions of greenhouse gases. About 40 % of all emissions from energy sources stem from the electricity industry. About 65 % of the energy goes into heating homes and water, and buildings account for about a quarter of all the equivalent CO₂-emissions due to their energy usage. Decarbonising the heating and cooling sector is a central task to achieving the energy transition.

Aluminium production is challenging due to a heavy reliance on fossil fuels today, process emissions from incumbent routes and high trade exposure. Aluminium smelting is one of the most energy-intensive industrial processes. In year 2022 worldwide production was around 60 million tonnes and total of 903 MWh was consumed for Al production. 50 % of energy was produced from coal, 34 % from hydro, 10 % from natural gas, 0.6 % from nuclear and 4.2 % from other renewables (International Aluminium Institute, 2022). Production facilities are well connected with the electrical grid and consequently they could balance power supply and demand, or they could act as grid balancing battery. Due to the high thermal inertia of the electrolytic process, only short duration interruptions are acceptable with manageable consequences (reduced metal production). The electrolytic process developed in the REVEAL project is expected to be even better manageable as described below. The power consumption of an aluminium smelter can be changed quickly by adjusting the output DC voltage of the rectifier.

Wind and solar energy sources are not constantly available and predictable due to their intermittent nature. Moreover, wind and solar energy sources are not uniformly distributed through the year and therefore seasonal storage proposed in the REVEAL project plays an important role for future grid stability. Overall, the integration of intermittent renewable energy sources affects the power systems in three ways (Brouwer et al., 2016):

1. physically (how power generators are dispatched)
2. economically (whether the business cases of all generators are sound)
3. security of supply (whether the power system meets its reliability targets)

Energy that is in excess and dumped is wasted. Hypothetically, future deployment of small smelters facilities near renewable sources worldwide, using REVEAL technology, could harvest most of intermittent/excess renewable energy and store it for later use, also over longer timespans over seasons.

The pace of renewable capacity growth in Europe will more than double in 2023-2028 compared with the previous six years, with additions totalling 532 GW. Solar PV accounts for over 70 % of the expansion, led by distributed systems, which is one-third more than utility-scale. Wind accounts for another 26 % led by

onshore projects (International Energy Agency, 2023). According to national energy and climate plans, the main contributors for EU renewable energy harvesting in 2030 are Germany and Spain (Table 2.1).

TABLE 1:1 WIND AND SOLAR CAPACITY TARGETS IN ELECTRICITY INSTALLED CAPACITY, BY COUNTRY FOR 2030 (EUROPEAN UNION, 2024).

Country	Wind [GW]	Solar [GW]
Germany	145	215
France	37	54
Spain	62	76
Italy	28	80
Netherlands	23	25

As mentioned above, societies will need to cut greenhouse gas emissions by replacing carbon-based energy sources with renewable and sustainable energy sources. However, the use of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar will require future energy dependent industries to be flexible in the utilisation of energy due to the intermittent nature of the renewable energy sources.

This report will highlight the flexibility and compatibility of the Power-to-Alu and Alu-to-Energy of the REVEAL project with local and distributed energy production.

2. Flexibility of Power-to-Alu with Hall-Hérout process

2.1 Power modulation

The traditional technology for primary aluminium production also called the Hall-Hérout process involves the electrolytic reduction of alumina (Al_2O_3) in a molten fluoride electrolyte consisting mainly of cryolite (Na_3AlF_6) contained in an electrochemical reduction cell at a temperature of ca. 960 °C. The electrochemical reduction cell consists of carbon anodes, which are consumed and conduct electrical current to the electrolyte and the cathode. The relatively high temperature of the fluoride electrolyte is provided and maintained through the resistive heating of the electrolyte, carbon anodes and other components. The overall reaction to produce aluminium by the Hall-Hérout process is described by Equation (2.1).

The Hall-Héroult technology is an energy intensive process with the average global direct current (DC) energy consumption being ca. 13.2 kWh/kg Al (Senanu et al., 2024).

Power modulation allows smelter operators to respond to changes in the electricity grid, electricity prices, or the availability of renewable energy sources by a flexible adjustment of the electrical power supplied to the cells. This is especially important as the aluminium industry must rely more on renewable energy sources like solar and wind that are intermittent nature. The main challenges faced by the traditional aluminium smelters are related to the electrolyte temperature and thermal balance of the electrolysis cells. A sketch giving the percentage heat distribution of the traditional aluminium electrolysis cell technology is given in Figure 2.1 below.

FIGURE 2.1 APPROXIMATE DISTRIBUTION OF THE HEAT LOSSES FROM A HALL-HÉROULT (HH) CELL. 76 % OF THE TOTAL HEAT IS GENERATED BELOW THE CRUST, 16 % IS GENERATED INSIDE THE SUPERSTRUCTURE, AND 8 % IN THE BUSBARS AND ANODE BEAM (SENANU ET AL., 2024)

It is crucial to maintain a suitable superheat (difference between the measured temperature and the liquidus temperature of the electrolyte) and thermal balance for optimal operations. The relatively high energy loss through the sidewalls is due to the requirement of a frozen ledge. This frozen ledge protects the sidewalls of the cell from the very corrosive nature of molten cryolite and aluminium.

(Wong et al., 2023) presented a simulation study of a short-term power modulation exercise using solar power supply. This is given by Figure 2.2 below where one can see that the line current was increased during daytime as solar power became available. The excess accumulated heat was then released at night when the ambient temperature was lowest and the rate of heat release from the cell is highest. The line current was reduced for a very short period (ca. 1 am to 5 am) to help bring the sideledge to the original thickness. The

very short time for current reduction implies maximum metal production. Thus, by adopting the right strategies, power modulation can help increase metal production.

FIGURE 2.2 BEHAVIOUR OF CELL STATES AND VARIABLES WITH ADDITIONAL SOLAR POWER SUPPLY DURING THE DAY AND SHORTER PERIODS OF HEAT RELEASE AT NIGHT WHEN AMBIENT TEMPERATURE IS LOW. (WONG ET. AL. 2023).

Figure 2.2 Behaviour of cell states and variables with additional solar power supply during the day and shorter periods of heat release at night when ambient temperature is low.

It is reported that power modulation can be done in different ways (Eisma and Patel, 2016):

- A complete shutdown of the electrolysis cell
- Putting cells to sleep (hibernation)
- Line amperage modulation.

All the different ways mentioned above can be applied to the inert anode technology employed in the REVEAL project.

A complete shutdown of the electrolysis cell will result in cooling and the consequent freezing of the electrolyte if done over a period of more than 3 hours making re-start very difficult after power is restored (Tabereaux, 2022). It has been shown that for the Hall-Héroult cell technology, the electrolyte temperature and superheat¹ required to keep the electrolyte in its liquid state drop drastically, leading to a negative superheat after ca. 1 hour of voltage reduction (Dupui, M et al., 2007). A negative superheat suggests freezing of the electrolyte. Figure 2.3 is extracted from the publication from Dupui et. al. and shows the drop in important cell parameters for the Hall-Héroult cell after a shutdown for 3 hours.

FIGURE 2.3 VARIATIONS IN VOLTAGE, ELECTROLYTE TEMPERATURE AND SUPERHEAT DURING POWER MODULATION (DUPUI, M ET AL., 2007)

The practice of putting cells to “sleep” or hibernation works with the traditional Hall-Héroult cells by lowering the anodes until they contact the aluminium metal pad (Tabereaux, 2022). Hibernating electrolysis cells can be done over a period of weeks and allows to drastically reduce the voltage on some selected cells to help manage the total voltage requirement of a whole potline during periods with reduced line amperages (Tabereaux, 2022) and (Eisma and Patel, 2016).

Line amperage modulation is a practice more widely used by aluminium smelters during peak power consumption periods and involves reduction of the line amperage by a predetermined value. Line amperage modulation allows a greater level of flexibility as smelter operators know how long it will take and when to do this. At smelters with several potlines, it can be decided to do line amperage modulation at one potline leaving the other potlines to produce normally thereby reducing potential damage or challenges to one

¹ the difference between the electrolyte and liquidus temperatures

potline. It is also possible to adopt different strategies for different potlines. Finally, line amperage modulations is currently used by some smelters to avoid extreme power costs during peak load hours (Eisma and Patel, 2016).

2.2 Shut down and hibernation.

A complete shutdown of the cell for “hibernation” would be required if the cell would only be used to convert and store excess electricity in summer and left unused in winter. This is unusual for conventional Hall-Héroult cells for several reasons:

- Cell cooling: The electrolysis cells begin to cool when the amperage is significantly reduced or completely curtailed. It is reported that the electrolyte temperature typically decreases at a rate of 15-20 °C per hour when the cell is shut down. The rapid decrease in electrolyte temperature is a direct result of the design of the cell. The HH electrolysis cell is designed to dissipate heat at the sidewalls to obtain the sideledge necessary to protect the cell linings from the corrosive mixture of molten cryolite and aluminium. The heat dissipation at the sidewalls continues almost at the same rate even after the amperage has been curtailed. The heat dissipation causes the electrolyte to cool when the source of the heat being the amperage is off. Eventually, the electrolyte will begin to freeze first before the molten aluminium due to the differences in their melting temperatures. Once the electrolyte and aluminium freezes in the cell, it becomes impossible to operate and will have to be dismantled.
- Cathode cooling cracks: The rapid cooling of HH electrolysis cells generates uneven temperature distribution in the cathode lining which results in thermally induced mechanical stresses within the cathode. These mechanical stresses can be enough to cause cracks on the cathode surface. The cracks have been observed to vary from 1.6 to 3 mm and often extend the whole length of the cathode blocks. Once a cathode block develops cracks it is very difficult to repair them for restart. Furthermore, the cracks weaken the cathode block as some may be filled with electrolyte and metal causing the cracks to expand and leading to failures during restart.

3. Flexibility of Power-to-Alu with Vertical inert electrodes

3.1 CO₂-free aluminium smelting with vertical inert electrodes

The ambition to achieve zero CO₂ emissions in the global aluminium industry aligns with Europe's goal for a sustainable circular economy. REVEAL partners, Arctus and IceTec, have pioneered a carbon-free aluminium production process. This innovative method utilizes vertical inert/non-consumable anodes and cathodes

within a low-temperature (800 ° C) electrolyte, resulting in the emission of oxygen rather than CO₂. The reaction to obtain aluminium from alumina (Al₂O₃) using the inert anode technology is given by Equation 3.1 below.

This approach has successfully demonstrated high-purity aluminium production (TRL 4), marking a significant advancement over traditional methods. Additionally, the process requires only a third of the cell size compared to conventional methods, resulting in substantial reductions in the need for cells, buildings, and materials. The inert electrodes process being developed has the potential to be at least 20 % more energy efficient than the conventional Hall-Héroult process and with no greenhouse gas emissions.

The design of scalable rectangular electrolytic vessels for the pilot plant for the aluminium process with vertical electrodes is faced with the following key challenges for safe and successful utilization:

1. Properly installed multiple vertical inert anodes and cathodes with electric connection.
2. Using both sides of the electrodes for conducting electricity.
3. Machinable and sealable sidewalls/bottom of the cells for a leak-free operation.
4. No contamination of the aluminium produced.
5. Withstands highly aggressive electrolyte solution, aluminium, and oxygen at 800 °C.
6. Proper thermal insulation.
7. Optimal low temperature (800 °C) electrolyte for dissolving the alumina.
8. Optimal alumina feeding and dissolution in the electrolyte with a control system.
9. Optimal metal tapping from the bottom of the cell.
10. Optimal lifetime of the inert electrodes.

FIGURE 3.1 ALUMINIUM PROCESS CELLS WITH MULTIPLE VERTICAL INERT ANODES AND CATHODES IN LOW TEMPERATURE ELECTROLYTE AT 800 °C. THIS PROCESS EMITS ONLY OXYGEN.

Low temperature electrolyte

Low temperature electrolytes for aluminium production are based on mixtures of NaF, KF and AlF_3 , where the compositions can be defined by a cryolite ratio (CR) defined the mole ratio $\text{CR} = (\text{KF} + \text{NaF}) / \text{AlF}_3$ and the KR ratio defined as the mole ratio $\text{KR} = \text{KF} / (\text{NaF} + \text{KF})$. Liquidus temperature in the system KF-NaF- AlF_3 for different value of CR is shown in Figure 3.2. This shows that liquidus temperature lower than 800 °C can be reached for all values of $\text{CR} = 1.3$ and even for $\text{CR} = 1.5$, considering that the liquidus temperature is lowered upon dissolution of alumina in the electrolyte.

At IceTec experiments have been carried out at different KR ratios of 0.3 and 0.8, at $\text{CR} = 1.3$ (Singh et al., 2023). For $\text{KR} = 0.3$ and $\text{CR} = 1.3$ the liquidus temperature is expected to be about 710 °C according to the data reported and shown in in Figure 3.2 (Aparov et al., 2011). With added alumina the liquidus temperature is expected to be even lower.

Superheat with this type of electrolyte is therefore in the order of 90 °C at $\text{KR} = 0.3$ and $\text{CR} = 1.3$, when electrolyte temperature is 800 °C. At $\text{KR} = 0.8$ and $\text{CR} = 1.3$ and superheat is expected to be slightly lower, at

the same temperature. The large superheat at 800 °C indicates that it can be acceptable to lower the operating temperature from 800 °C, to maybe 740 – 760 °C.

FIGURE 3.2 LIQUIDUS TEMPERATURE IN THE SYSTEM KF-NAF-ALF₃ SYSTEM FOR DIFFERENT VALUES OF CR. BASED ON FORMULAS EMPIRICAL FORMULAS FROM APISAROV ET AL. (APISAROV ET AL. 2011).

In small scale experiments (at 30 - 40 A) the electrolyte temperature is kept at target temperature by heating the electrolysis cell from outside in an electric furnace. Most the experiment at IceTec have been carried out at a liquidus temperature of 800 °C, but experiments have also been carried out where the electrolyte temperature has been changed within certain limits. The results of one experiment are show in Figure 3.3 where temperature was varied between 783 °C and 820 °C, where the experiments were also run at different current densities. The changes in current density are manifested by changes in cell voltage at each temperature, the higher the current density the higher the voltage. It is expected that the operating temperature can be as low as 740 °C and even up to 840 °C. The experiment described above was carried out in a 30 – 40 A electrolysis cell, with vertical CuNiFe inert anodes and TiB₂ cathodes, in which the furnace temperature was about 50 – 70 °C higher than the electrolysis temperature. In experiments that are carried out in larger 500 A electrolysis cells, furnace temperature can be several tenths of degrees lower than electrolyte temperature of 800 °C, depending on cell voltage (current density), demonstrating that there is heat transport from the electrolysis cell to the furnace.

In order to design a cell that is self-heating, i.e. does not require an outer furnace for heating, the total current to the cell probably needs to be of the order of 20.000 – 40.000 A. Full scale cells are expected to be operating

at 100.000 – 200.000 A and these could allow for much more flexibility in the operating temperature of the cell, and enable much greater opportunities for power modulation than conventional Hall-Héroult cells, which are designed for a superheat of about 10 °C. In inert electrode cells the superheat is expected to be about 70 – 90 °C, depending on electrolyte composition. A further advantage with inert electrode cell is that their temperature can likely be increase to 820 – 840 °C.

FIGURE 3.3 CELL VOLTAGE AND TEMPERATURE DURING AN ELECTROLYSIS TEST IN A SMALL ELECTROLYSIS CELL. TEMPERATURE WAS VARIED BETWEEN 783 °C AND 820 °C, AND EXPERIMENTS WERE RUN AT DIFFERENT ANODE CURRENT DENSITIES OF 0.4, 0.51 AND 0.6 A/CM₂. ELECTROLYTE COMPOSITION WAS CR = 1.3, KR= 0.3. (SINGH, GUNNARSSON ET AL. 2023)

Ledge free cell sidewalls for energy reduction

The benefits of aluminium electrolysis cells with vertical inert anodes and wettable cathodes (vertical inert electrode cells) are best realised in well insulated ledge free electrolysis cells which should have much lower thermal losses through sidewalls and bottom than conventional cells, described in Figure 2.1. Vertical inert electrode cells are also expected to be much smaller than HH cells of the same capacity and the electrolyte temperature is ca. 160 °C lower. Both factors contribute to lower thermal losses.

The energy consumption of inert electrode cells will depend on any many factors, as for example current density, electrolyte composition, anode cathode distance, cell design etc. These remain to be optimized for the inert anode cells. As shown in Figure 3.3, cell voltage can be lower than 4 V, which is similar to that of the best HH cells, which have been optimised for over 100 years.

3.2 Energy consumption

An inert electrode process is based on a different total cell reaction than the traditional Hall-Héroult process. Since the Gibbs free enthalpy of the inert electrode process (eq. 3.1) is higher than the one of the HH process (eq. 2.1) also the standard potential (voltage) of the inert process is higher. This means that under the assumption of identical internal resistance and losses of the cell, more electric energy will be needed for the new process. This additional electric energy can be seen as a replacement or compensation for the energy input by carbon anodes of the HH process that is not needed anymore in the new process. However, due to the possibility to reduce the anode-cathode distance and other optimizations such as ledge free sidewalls, the total energy input (electric and carbon) can be lowered with the new process. Current estimations are a total energy input of 17 kWh/kg Al (of which 3.8 kWh is from the carbon anodes and 13.2 kWh is the DC electric energy) in the best-practice traditional process, compared to the estimated 12.5-14.4 kWh (DC electric energy = total) for the scaled up inert electrode process, which corresponds to savings of 15-25 % of energy and 100 % of direct CO₂-emissions. This applies for the electrolysis process, if production of electrodes for the process is included, the savings are expected to be considerably higher.

3.3 Power modulation with frozen ledge sidewalls in cells

In REVEAL we have studied the minimal energy consumption, both theoretically and practically for electrolytic cells with vertical inert electrodes in low temperature (800 °C) electrolyte for aluminium production. “Modular power feeding” during peak hours has also been studied for optimal power price by reducing the line current and power to the cells and at the same time increase the cell resistance and voltage by lifting the anodes to keep sufficient thermal stability in the cell.

Traditional smelters have over the years investigated the flexibility of the HH cell using different strategies. As an example, Trimet has been able to demonstrate highly flexible energy input of up to ± 25 % in a modified test section of 12 reduction pots with Shell Heat Exchanger (SHE) technology at their smelter in Essen, Germany. The flexibility exercise enabled some of their pots to operate with +20/-13 % energy input for up to 48 hours while staying within optimal process condition (Depree et al., 2016).

There are significant benefits for an aluminium smelter with vertical inert anodes and cathodes in 800 °C electrolyte as well as for the power suppliers if it is easy to significantly reduce the short-term power to the

cells with enough thermal stability in the cells to dissolve the alumina. Of course, aluminium production will be reduced during this period. We have tried to estimate the possible power modulations in aluminium production cells with vertical electrodes with frozen ledge sidewalls and ledge free sidewalls, see Table 3.1.

TABLE 3.1 ALUMINIUM SMELTERS FLEXIBILITY OF POWER CONSUMPTION BY POWER MODULATION

Time period	REVEAL* Inert Electrodes Frozen Ledge Cell	REVEAL** Inert Electrodes Ledge Free Cell
1 hour	+/- 30 %	+/- 35 %
3 hours	+/- 25 %	+/- 30 %
10 hours	+/- 18 %	+/- 21 %
24 hours	+/- 7 %	+/- 10 %
1 week	+/- 2 %	+/- 4 %

* REVEAL inert electrodes frozen ledge cells estimation

** REVEAL inert electrodes ledge free cells estimation

The REVEAL electrolysis cell is designed to be ca. 1/3 the size of the conventional HH cell with the same production capacity. The smaller size of the REVEAL cell reduces the total heat losses arising from heat transfer out of the cell and consequently reduces the total power consumption.

3.4 Power modulation with ledge-free sidewalls in cells

One possible and very interesting object of the invention with vertical electrode cell with low temperature (800 °C) electrolyte system is the possibility to operate the cell without a frozen sidewall or ledge of salt if suitable ceramic material is developed in order to avoid corrosion of the sidewalls. Such a development is ongoing.

In conventional Hall Héroult frozen ledge cells, the heat losses account for ca. 50 % of the total energy input.

Due to size and less surface area of cells with vertical inert electrodes the heat loss is reduced. Furthermore, the cells with ledge free sidewalls can be well insulated on the outside and will therefore be able to keep the heat in the cell for a longer period during power modulation. This gives a higher level of flexibility for power modulation relative to the traditional cells that rely on frozen ledges.

4. Flexibility of Alu-to-Energy – low temperature route

The production of heat and hydrogen and subsequently heat and electricity from Alu-to-Energy is a relatively new and young research area and therefore little to no information has been published up to now on the

flexibility of Alu-to-Energy and its integration into energy systems with fluctuating production from renewables.

The process for the production of heat and electricity involves two main components:

1. The Alu-to-H₂ reactor for the conversion of aluminium to hydrogen, aluminium-hydroxide and heat
2. The PEM fuel cell that converts hydrogen to electricity and heat

In the first process, half of the energy stored in the aluminium fuel is transferred to energy stored in hydrogen, the other half is released as heat. In the second process around half of the energy stored in the hydrogen is converted to electricity, the other half adds to the heat output of the overall system. In total, from the energy stored in aluminium around 75 % can be used as heat and 25 % as electricity, subtracting losses and self-consumption of electricity the values may be 5-10 % (relative) lower.

In order to estimate the reaction time for ramping up or down electricity production the reaction time of the Alu-to-H₂ reactor as well as the reaction time of the PEM fuel cell is assessed. Fuel cells, when ready, can react relatively fast and adapt electricity production within a few seconds. For example, the fuel cell system chosen for this project needs from a cold state 30 seconds to warm-up and another 30 seconds to produce at nominal capacity. The power electronics for conversion of DC power to AC that can be fed to the grid is much faster and, properly done, qualifies for primary balancing power of grids. Therefore, the critical, i.e. slowest component of the process chain is the Alu-to-Energy reactor and the focus in the following sections is exclusively on this device and the supply of hydrogen to the fuel cell.

The rate of hydrogen production from aluminium water reaction depends on several factors:

1. Type of alloy, i.e. concentration of foreign metals in the aluminium alloy
2. Shape of the aluminium particles
3. Alkalinity or other concentration of protective oxide layer braking substance
4. Temperature

Figure shows the evolvement of the aluminium water reaction based on simulations with the model that was developed within REVEAL for the low temperature reaction scheme for two different alloys under identical conditions of shape (particles > 0.5 mm), alkalinity and temperature. It can be seen that:

- a) the type of alloy has a significant effect on the reaction rate
- b) a fast-reacting alloy completes reaction within about 15 minutes, even for a particle size > 0.5 mm

FIGURE 4.1: EVOLVEMENT OF THE ALUMINIUM-WATER REACTION FOR TWO DIFFERENT ALUMINIUM ALLOYS FOR THE SAME BOUNDARY CONDITIONS OF SHAPE, ALKALINITY, AND TEMPERATURE: ALU-XXXX ALLOY SELECTED BY OST, RIGHT: ALLOY OF TYPE 7'000 ACCORDING TO DIN EN 573-3.

A fast reaction rate as shown in Figure for the alloy selected by OST can be achieved at a temperature of 80 °C. Consequently:

- Hydrogen production can be ramped up within 15 minutes from a warm and ready system (80 °C)
- For a cold-start, additional time has to be taken into account for heating from ambient to 80 °C.

4.1 Warm start

Results of a simulation of hydrogen production with the selected aluminium alloy and shape at a temperature of 80 °C can be seen in Figure . The simulation assumed Al-feeding of equal amounts at intervals of 1 minute. It can be seen that the hydrogen production reaches maximum after 15-20 minutes, and after the feeding stops, hydrogen production fades out within another 20 minutes. An immediate start of electricity production at nominal power from the fuel cell could be achieved by the inclusion of a hydrogen buffer tank. In order to bridge the gap between start of the first aluminium dosing and maximum or nominal production rate, an amount of hydrogen would be needed that is equivalent to 5.1 minutes of full hydrogen production of the system. For a system that produces 4 kW_{tot} (1 kW_{el} + 3 kW_{th}), the hydrogen production rate is 51 g/h and the buffer needed to compensate for time to ramp-up production corresponds to 4.3 g or 56 L hydrogen (@ 1 bar(a), 20 °C), or 11 L (@ 5 bar(a), 20 °C).

FIGURE 4.2: SIMULATION OF RELATIVE PRODUCTION RATE AFTER START OF SYSTEM WITH A FEEDING INTERVAL OF 1 DOSE OF ALUMINIUM GRAINS PER MINUTE FOR 20 MINUTES, AT A TEMPERATURE OF 80 °C.

4.2 Cold start

For the cold start, the system needs to be heated up before the hydrogen production reaches a high rate. At room temperatures the production starts very slowly even at high alkaline conditions and with a favourable alloy. For this reason, it is assumed in the following that the addition of aluminium granules only begins once the operating temperature of 80 °C has been reached.

In principle, there are two options for heating up the reaction vessel if it is assumed that the system is not connected to the power grid or does not draw energy from the grid. Option one would be to utilise the waste heat from the fuel cell power system that is already producing electricity from a hydrogen buffer before hydrogen is supplied from the aluminium-water reaction. This would require a (larger) hydrogen buffer tank for the heating process. The second option would be to use a battery to heat the reaction vessel directly with an electric heater. As the exact geometry of the reaction vessel is not known at the time of preparing this deliverable, the energy required for the heating process is determined on the basis of a reactor of 10 cm inner diameter and 25 cm height. Based on this configuration, the mass for steel and water and their corresponding heat capacities is calculated. Considering 15 % heat losses, it is assumed that around 185 Wh are required for the process of heating from 20 °C to 80 °C.

With option one, at nominal load of the fuel cell power system and an assumed fuel cell system efficiency of 50 %, around 1 kW of thermal power is available for heating the reaction vessel. At this power, the warm-up

process would take ca. 11.5 min. To operate the fuel cell system at nominal power for this period, 9.5 g of hydrogen is needed. Assuming a storage pressure of 5 bar, a buffer tank with this capacity would have a volume of around 23 litres. With this approach, a system that would deliver electricity from start (i.e. only delay of fuel cell of 30-60 seconds) would need a reservoir of hydrogen at 5 bars with 23 litres for warming up plus 11 litres to bridge the gap until full production, i.e. a total of 34 litres. While the fuel cell consumes the first 23 litres of hydrogen, only the heat output is used for warming up, the electricity produced can already be fed to the grid or load of the house.

With option two, the thermal power for the heating process is provided by a direct electric heater and a battery. To make the two options comparable, it is assumed that the heating output is 1 kW (thermal or electric). If a lithium-ion battery with a voltage of 300 V is used, it must be possible to discharge the battery with a current of 3.3 A. With an assumed C-rate of 0.7 and a Depth of Discharge of 90 %, a battery with a capacity of 5.3 Ah is required. Consequently, a battery with 1.6 kWh must be used in order to achieve a heating output comparable to that of option 1. If during warming up 1 kW of electricity should already be provided to the grid or load, the capacity of the battery would need to be doubled (i.e. 3.2 kWh). Additionally, an 11 litres hydrogen buffer would be needed for bridging the gap to full scale production of hydrogen from aluminium-water reaction. In order to avoid this hydrogen buffer and to cover the electricity production also during this time, an equal amount of electricity would need to be delivered additionally by the battery, which is 5.1 minutes of 1 kW_{el} or 0.85 kWh. This would increase the battery size to 4.05 kWh.

4.3 Sleep mode

When the system is in sleep mode, the fuel cell needs to be properly conditioned to protect the active membrane from drying out and to keep out unwanted gases. Also, the Alu-to-Energy system needs to maintain a certain overpressure of hydrogen gas inside the system in order to avoid atmospheric air and oxygen from entering, which would need nitrogen purging before restart. However, the operating temperature of 60-80 °C does not have to be maintained for either of the two systems, which means that also longer periods in sleep mode without significant energy consumption or energy loss are possible.

5. Flexibility of Alu-to-Energy – high temperature route

Adaptability of the Alu-to-Energy reactor system gives options for integration into single/multi house energy systems and for industrial use, in terms of heat and hydrogen production. High temperature route request reactor to burn the fuel (Al granules) and system to use the energy.

The high temperature route produces heat and electricity via two main steps. The first step involves the reaction of aluminium to produce heat and hydrogen while the second step involves producing electricity using PEM. The ratio of heat and electricity produced is calculated to be roughly the same. However, the high temperature route converts aluminium to aluminium oxide while hydroxide is produced in the low temperature route.

Regarding flexibility, the same applies as for the low temperature route, PEM prepared in standby mode, can respond quickly and adjust their power output in a matter of seconds. When implemented correctly, the power electronics used to transform direct current (DC) into alternating current (AC) for distribution to the grid are both speedier and eligible to serve as the grid's principal balancing power. Thus, the high temperature Alu-to-Energy reactor system is a “bottle neck” and its role in supplying hydrogen to the fuel cell will be the sole subjects of discussion in the sections that follow. It is worth to mention that heat produced in that first process step could be stored in normal water heat storage and used on demand.

5.1 Warm start

In case that the high temperature (operational temperature 450 °C) reactor is stopped for a certain time the reactor is purged by nitrogen (excluding water or steam as reactant). The release of hydrogen after steam supply is within 1-3 minutes. The production of hydrogen is related to the feeding rate. If continuous feeding is applied, then the hydrogen release rate is constant. If there is no continuous feeding, reaction peaks are dependent on working pressure and temperature. Higher pressure and temperature enable faster reaction and a peak will follow changes in feeding in less than an hour. By incorporating a hydrogen buffer tank, the fuel cell could initiate the generation of energy almost without any delay.

5.2 Cold start

Prior to reaching a high rate of hydrogen production, the system must be heated and pressurized for the cold start. The heating up to operating conditions depends on the power of the heating element used. After reaching the operating temperature and pressure, production of hydrogen increases with time. Figure 5.1 represents the hydrogen output as a function of time for certain temperature and pressure.

FIGURE 5.1 REACTION TIME AS A FUNCTION OF VOLUME OF HYDROGEN GAS RELEASE.

From Figure 5.1 it is evident that if the pressure and temperature are high enough, reaction may complete within 1 – 5 hours.

6. Conclusion

REVEAL is a research project, currently on the technology readiness level 3 (TRL3). The low TRL implies there is still a long road to get to TRL9 and verify/prove the system in operational environment. However, we are likely to see both technical developments on that road which will enhance the system flexibility and economic boundaries to operational flexibility. Despite the low TRL, the REVEAL project has provided results and vision on system flexibility and the challenges in maximizing system operational flexibility.

European primary aluminium smelters have been developing enhanced flexibility and adapting to electricity market with intermittent renewable energy sources. The cells must be held at nearly the same temperature which limits the operational flexibility. Still, the flexibility available can be valuable in the local community. The inert anode concept with vertical electrode configuration developed in REVEAL is operated at a lower electrolyte temperature (800 °C) due to the relatively low liquidus temperature of the electrolyte which gives a superheat that is up to 8 times higher than that of the conventional process which is operated at ca. 960 °C.

Furthermore, the relatively low temperature of the REVEAL process provides an option to increase the electrolyte temperature prior to power interruptions without compromising the stability of the lining material. The high superheat combined with the low electrolyte temperatures allows for much more flexibility in process operation and adaption to using intermittent renewable energy sources. Moreover, if further development of the inert anode technology allows operation in a well-insulated ledge-free cell, the flexibility will be further improved. However, an operation based on seasonal excess energy that involves stopping the operation during a season is not foreseen. This is due to the high costs relating to shutting down, hibernating, and restarting the operation of aluminium electrolysis cells after longer periods.

On the other hand, the Alu-to-Energy process or discharging is quite flexible and can be stopped and left to stand also for weeks and months. Once needed, ramping up can be done in less than an hour from cold start and within 20 minutes from warm start, and electric output power modulation is expected to be limited only by the capabilities of the connected fuel cell if the system includes a small hydrogen buffer that evens out temporary mismatches between hydrogen production and consumption.

Whereas the Power-to-Alu or charging process is considered to be an industrial application that will be performed in large, centralized plants, the Alu-to-Energy or discharging process is quite modular and scalable and is expected to be possible in small decentralized systems of few kW power as well as in larger MW-scale plants.

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